

**THE MEDIATING EFFECT OF SELF-REGULATION ON THE RELATIONSHIP
BETWEEN MATHEMATICAL DISPOSITION AND MATHEMATICS
PROFICIENCY AMONG MATHEMATICS
EDUCATION STUDENTS**

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 30

Issue 8

Pages: 1358-1375

Document ID: 2025PEMJ2916

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14642045

Manuscript Accepted: 12-06-2024

The Mediating Effect of Self-Regulation on the Relationship between Mathematical Disposition and Mathematics Proficiency among Mathematics Education Students

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to determine whether self-regulation mediates the relationship between mathematical disposition and mathematics proficiency among first-year mathematics major students. The study was quantitative non-experimental research that utilizes descriptive-correlational, and mediation analysis. Using stratified random sampling, specifically proportional allocation, for the sampling techniques and Slovin's formula with 0.05 margin of error for the sample size, a sample of 92 randomly selected mathematics education students answered the surveys on the three variables. Results showed that the level of mathematical disposition and the mediating variable, self-regulation, are all at high level; the level of mathematics proficiency, which was measured through a 25-item multiple-choice questionnaire, is at a very good or satisfactory level. Results also revealed that the relationship between mathematical disposition and mathematics proficiency, between mathematical disposition and self-regulation, and between self-regulation and mathematics proficiency among first-year mathematics education students are all significant. However, results showed that self-regulation did not mediate the relationship between mathematical disposition and mathematics proficiency as the indirect effect has a p-value greater than 0.5 or null accepted. It implied that mathematical disposition directly influences mathematics proficiency without the intervention of self-regulation. This finding underscored the complexity of factors influencing mathematical proficiency and suggests avenues for further research to better understand the mechanisms at play. Understanding these relationships can inform interventions and educational strategies aimed at improving mathematics proficiency.

Keywords: *mathematical disposition, mathematics proficiency, self-regulation, mediation analysis, Philippines*

Introduction

Mathematics proficiency with algebra is difficult for students, even those who are in their college degree (Powell et al., 2019). Students dealing with numbers and math might feel like they are in a confusing world. Further, complicated formulas and tricky numbers often make them see the difficulty instead of understanding the true meaning and importance of math. These challenges have been persistent in the field of mathematics (Naungayan, 2022). Unfortunately, the current crisis in education has been exacerbated by the COVID-19 pandemic, which has increased the mathematics learning gap among young students (Sooknanan & Seemungal, 2023). The event has caused a drop in math learning, as students might need extra help before moving on to new lessons, resulting in gaps in their knowledge (Torres, 2021). However, schools and educators should take action to address this issue by using strategies to boost students' motivation and disposition in learning math, offering extra help to struggling students, and using technology to support remote learning. Despite the challenges, it is very important to focus on closing the learning gaps and improving the mathematics skills of the students.

In Fiji, poor performance in mathematics is a serious concern at the senior level of secondary schools in the Ba and Tavua districts (Chand et al., 2021). Also, in the United States, the National Center for Education Statistics reported that national math exam results were particularly alarming, showing the sharpest declines ever recorded on the nation's report card. In the first test results since the pandemic began, math scores for eighth graders dropped in nearly every state (Mervosh & Wu, 2022).

In the Philippines, the Filipino students were among the lowest performing groups in the 2018 Program for International Student Assessment (PISA). Majority of the Filipino students (80.70%) had proficiency levels below Level 2, with 54.4% below Level 1. Only 19.7% of students reached proficiency levels 2 to 4 (Department of Education, 2019). Furthermore, the results on the 2022 PISA were about the same as in the 2018 PISA in mathematics, revealing no significant improvements among the Filipino students' performance (Hernando-Malipot, 2023).

A growing number of employments in today's technologically dependent world require some degree of expertise in mathematics. Hence, this study shows relevance to the current issue as this would contribute to resolving the mathematics education crisis, determining the underlying factors influencing the mathematics proficiency among students in the post-pandemic era. As the problem regarding the lack of mathematical proficiency of students across the globe is constantly emerging, this has to be taken an immediate action. Additionally, Filipino students scoring below the lowest proficiency level in the PISA indicates they have fallen significantly behind in mathematics education. Most Filipino students lack the necessary mathematical skills compared to their peers in other parts of the world.

In review, there are already related studies that had been conducted in different designs and approaches. In fact, Hutajulu et al. (2019) conducted a study entitled, "Improving of Mathematical Proficiency and Disposition Using Multi Representation Approach on Vocational Students" which aims to oversee the improvement and achievement of mathematical disposition and proficiency of vocational students using multi-representation approach. Another, a study entitled, "The Logical Thinking Ability: Mathematical

Disposition and Self-regulated Learning” by Ab et al. (2019) had conducted with the purpose of analyzing the direct effect of factors from the logical thinking ability. Further, a study entitled, “Self-Regulation of Mathematical Knowledge and Skills” was conducted to discuss the effectiveness of self-regulated learning training in mathematics (De Corte et al., 2011). The existing studies show the connections between the variables present in this paper. However, this study is exclusively unique from the aforementioned studies because there is no existing study that examine the self-regulation as a mediator between the linkage of mathematical disposition and mathematics proficiency. Hence, the aforementioned studies indicate that this current study does not show irrelevance and redundancy.

Lastly, this study will contribute to the body of literature not only within the four corners of the institution but also beyond in it as copies of the study, including its findings, will be disseminated to the various research conferences and related agencies to facilitate scholarly exchange and utilization of research-based discovery. Ergo, the significance and findings of this study would be realized by the broader community through making actions and solutions on the problems being discussed as well as implementing the recommendations being suggested here.

Research Objectives

The aim of this study was to determine the mediating role of self-regulation on the relationship between mathematical disposition and mathematics proficiency of Mathematics Education student. Specifically, this attempted to achieve the following objectives:

1. To determine the level of mathematical disposition in terms of:
 - 1.1. cognitive;
 - 1.2. affective; and
 - 1.3. conative.
2. To determine the level of mathematics proficiency.
3. To determine the level of self-regulation in terms of:
 - 3.1. intrinsic;
 - 3.2. identified;
 - 3.3. introjected; and
 - 3.4. external.
4. To determine the significant relationship between:
 - 4.1. mathematical disposition and mathematics proficiency;
 - 4.2. mathematical disposition and self-regulation; and
 - 4.3. self-regulation and mathematics proficiency.
5. To determine the mediating effect of self-regulation on the relationship between mathematical disposition and mathematics proficiency.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a quantitative non-experimental research design utilizing a descriptive-correlational technique alongside mediation analysis. The investigation focused on mediating variables, which are characterized as behavioral, biological, psychological, or social constructs that facilitate the transfer of the effect of one variable to another. This approach aimed to comprehend the mechanisms underlying the influence of one variable on another. Non-experimental research, as described, did not involve the manipulation of an independent variable or the random assignment of individuals to conditions or sequences of conditions. It is acknowledged that categorizing these methods solely based on what they are not might be unfair (Price et al., 2014).

In this study, non-experimental methods to investigate the relationship between mathematical disposition, self-regulation, and mathematics proficiency among mathematics education students, providing insights for educational strategies, the study can offer valuable insights into how attitude towards mathematics and self-management affect performance on the subject, which can inform educational strategies and curriculum development in teacher education programs.

Furthermore, descriptive studies were crucial in the research design as they provided tools to summarize, analyze, and comprehend data. They offered insights into central tendencies, variability, and distribution of data. Measures like mean, median, and mode provided average values, while measures like range, variance, and standard deviation revealed data dispersion. Tools like histograms, box plots, and frequency tables visualized data distribution. They aided in data-driven decisions, identifying trends, and communicating findings effectively (Price et al., 2014).

In this study, descriptive statistics were utilized to efficiently summarize and analyze gathered data, providing insights into the central tendencies, variability, and distribution of mathematical disposition, self-regulation, and mathematics proficiency within the participant group. These statistics served as a foundation for understanding complex dynamics and identifying patterns, contributing to meaningful conclusions in the study.

Then, on the other hand, correlational research is characterized as a type of non-experimental study where the researcher analyzes two

variables and assesses their statistical relationship or correlation with minimal or no attempt to control extraneous factors. There were two primary reasons why researchers who were interested in statistical correlations between variables might prefer to perform a correlational rather than an experimental study (Price et al., 2014).

In the context, correlational research proves valuable in examining statistical relationships between variables like mathematical disposition, self-regulation, and mathematics proficiency without manipulating them in a controlled environment. This approach acknowledges the complexity of real-world educational settings, providing insights crucial for tailoring effective teaching strategies to support students' success in mathematics within the constraints of a non-experimental approach.

Mediation analysis, in its simplest form, represented the addition of a third variable to the $X \rightarrow Y$ relation, whereby X caused the mediator, M , and caused Y , so $X \rightarrow M \rightarrow Y$. This analytical approach provided a deeper understanding of the mechanisms through which the independent variable affected the dependent variable. By identifying and exploring the role of the mediator, researchers gained insights into the underlying processes and pathways that contributed to the observed relationship between X and Y . Mediation analysis was particularly valuable in uncovering the intervening variables that explained how and why changes in X led to changes in Y .

In this context, the researcher explored the intricate connections between multiple intelligences (X), learning styles (M), and mathematical proficiency (Y). The analysis revealed a relationship ($X \rightarrow M \rightarrow Y$), illustrating how self-regulation mediate the influence of mathematical disposition on mathematics proficiency. These insights are crucial for customizing teaching strategies and curriculum to optimize mathematical learning in our specific educational context.

The independent variable in this study was mathematical disposition, while the dependent variable was mathematics proficiency, and the mediating variable was self-regulation. In this study, the researcher determined the relationship between mathematical disposition and mathematics proficiency, and the mediating effect of self-regulation on the relationship between mathematical disposition and mathematics proficiency among mathematics education students.

Respondents

The respondents of this study were the first-year mathematics education students from Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology located at the Municipality of Kapalong, Province of Davao del Norte.

Further, Table 1 showed the distribution of the respondents of this study. Hence, to ensure an accurate distribution of samples, the researcher employed stratified random sampling, utilizing proportional allocation, through Slovin's formula with a margin of error of 0.05. In stratified random sampling, the population is first divided into distinct subgroups known as "strata". Within each of these strata, a method of uniform random sampling is utilized to select a sample. Subsequently, the individual samples from each stratum are combined to create the overall stratified random sample (Nguyen et al, 2020). In this case, the strata are the two sections of first-year mathematics education program in Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology (KCAST).

In addition, the total respondents of the study were taken from two first-year sections of mathematics education program. To ensure an appropriate sample for the study, the statistician calculated the sample size, resulting in the selection of 49 out of 63 students from BSED- Mathematics 1A, and 43 out of 56 students from BSED-Mathematics 1B. In total, 92 were sampled out of 119 first-year mathematics education students.

The criterion of selecting the respondents is the following: the respondents must be enrolled in the first semester of the academic year 2023-2024 under BSED-Mathematics program in Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology, Also, must have sufficient engagement in learning mathematics in their junior and senior high school years.

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents*

<i>Program/Section</i>	<i>Population</i>	<i>Sample</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
BSEd-Mathematics 1A	63	49	41%
BSEd-Mathematics 1B	56	43	36%
Total	119	92	77%

Instrument

The Likert scale, a common study rating tool, measured the thoughts of individuals on a topic. The scale usually included a series of statements or questions with response options to indicate respondents' agreement or disagreement. The response options ranged from "strongly agree" to "strongly disagree," with numerous severity levels. Social science researchers employed the Likert scale in behavioral, educational, and health settings (Spector, 1992).

This study used a Likert scale to assess respondents' responses to these dimensions' assertions. Using a Likert scale, respondents' agreement or disagreement with each statement was quantified to assess academic commitment, behavioral engagement, and instructional aid. Since experts confirmed the Likert scales, the researcher was able to analyze the data and study how behavioral engagement mediates the relationship between academic dedication and instructional support.

Also, the dependent variable in this study, mathematics proficiency, was measured using a multiple-choice question format. Multiple Choice Questions (MCQs) are widely acknowledged as the most versatile and effective type of objective test items. They are capable of assessing essential educational outcomes, including knowledge, understanding, judgment, and problem-solving skills (Al-Rukban, 2006).

The study adopted three questionnaires from web sources to measure the variables. The instrument for mathematical disposition is from the study of Alghazo et. al. (2013), entitled, “An Analysis of Pre-Service Teachers’ Dispositions Towards Mathematics”. The Mathematics Dispositional Functioning Inventory (MDFI) which is being used in the study specifically designed to measure mathematical dispositions as described by Beyers (2011). The MDFI measures three categories related to mathematics disposition: conative, cognitive, and affective. This instrument has been rigorously developed and tested to ensure its reliability and validity, with the authors reporting an internal validity coefficient of .90, which indicates that the instrument is very beneficial, and .938 for reliability which implies that the instrument is excellent to be used in studies. In describing the mathematical disposition of the students, the following five-point Likert type scale was used.

Also, the instrument for the mathematics proficiency is from the study of Awaji (2021) which is Investigating the Effectiveness of Using GeoGebra Software on Students’ Mathematical Proficiency. The mathematics proficiency questionnaire is in the form of problem-solving type. It was measured with 25 items and the scores that can be obtained ranging from 0–25. Higher scores indicate higher mathematics proficiency.

The instrument used for measuring self-regulation is from the study entitled, “A Differential Item Functioning Analysis of the German Academic Self-Regulation Questionnaire for Adolescents” by Gnambs and Hanfstingl (2014). This self-regulation questionnaire encompasses four domains: intrinsic (five items), identified (five items), introjected (five items), and external (five items). The latent factor reliabilities for these domains, according to Hancock and Mueller (2001), are .94, .93, .83, and .79, respectively, indicating satisfactory reliability. A five-point Likert type scale was used for the self-assessment questionnaire.

To ensure the content validity of the survey research questionnaire, a thorough validation process was conducted. The initial draft of the research instrument was submitted to the research committee, which provided valuable feedback, recommendations, and suggestions for improving its presentation. This iterative review process helped refine the questionnaire to better capture the intended constructs and ensure its appropriateness for the study’s objectives. The committee’s input was also carefully considered, and necessary corrections was made based on their recommendations. Additionally, an item analysis was performed on the multiple-choice test for mathematics proficiency. This analysis helped determine which items should be retained and which ones should be discarded, ensuring the test’s accuracy and relevance. Also, some items were added to replace the discarded items.

Subsequently, the revised questionnaire was submitted to the research panel for final review and revision. The expert validators had thoroughly examined the final draft, identifying errors, providing suggestions, and offering comments to further enhance its quality. These valuable inputs from the validators were then incorporated into the questionnaire before proceeding with data collection.

To assess the questionnaire’s overall effectiveness, the evaluations and assessments from the expert validators was consolidated. This comprehensive analysis allowed for a comprehensive understanding of the questionnaire’s status and ensured its reliability for the study.

In assessing mathematics proficiency for the total score of the mathematical proficiency problem-solving test type, this study adapted the range of scores for 25-item test from the study of Batang and Temporal (2018).

Procedure

In collecting the data, the researcher had observed the following steps:

Seeking the Permission to Conduct the Study. The researcher sought permission from the College President of KCAST through a letter to allow the researcher to conduct the study among first-year mathematics education students. After getting the approval of the College President, the researcher sent the letters to the College Registrar and the Vice-President for Academic Affairs. Then, the researcher notified the program coordinator of the Bachelor of Secondary Education—Mathematics, as well as to the panel members for them to be fully aware of the conduct of the study.

Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire. Upon the approval of the College President, the researcher sought assistance from the program coordinator of Bachelor of Secondary Education major in Mathematics as well as their respective class mayors for the dissemination of the questionnaire through face-to-face.

Collection and Tabulation of the Data. This time, the research instrument was retrieved, examined, accumulated for the tabulation of the data being gathered. Since 92 students were recognized as first-year mathematics education students, the researcher found it convenient.

Data Analysis

The following statistical tools were used in the computation of data and testing the hypotheses. It includes mean, Pearson r, and

structural equation modeling using mediation analysis.

Mean. This statistical tool was used to determine the level of mathematical disposition, mathematics proficiency, and self-regulation.

Pearson r. This statistical tool was utilized to test the relationship between mathematical disposition and mathematics proficiency; mathematical disposition and self-regulation; and self-regulation and mathematics proficiency.

Structural Equation Modeling using Mediation Analysis. This statistical tool was carried out to figure out whether the mediating variable has any impact on the relationship between independent variable and a dependent variable using indirect effect. It was utilized in this research to find out if self-regulation mediated the relationship between mathematical disposition and mathematics proficiency by answering the mean statement of the problem. Specifically, this study utilized the Preacher and Hayes approach.

Ethical Considerations

The participants of this study were first-year mathematics education students in Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology. In this case, the researcher ensured that their safety, rights, and trust upon the researcher and the purpose of the study were given rightful action and justice.

It is necessary for researcher to uphold high ethical standards when doing research with the involvement of human participants. The primary objective of this quantitative investigation is to ensure the ethical soundness of the study in order to protect the welfare of human participants. The researcher reflected how the research in all aspects is able to adhere to the following considerations from Denzin and Lincoln (2011) which focused on three core principles: informed consent; risk of harm, anonymity, and confidentiality; as well as conflict of interest.

Informed consent is the first core principles of ethical considerations. The requirements, the planned use of the data, and any potential ramifications must all be adequately disclosed to participants. Participants must express their explicit, active, and written consent to participate in the study. They must also acknowledge that they are aware of their right to access their information and that they have the right to revoke their consent at any time. An agreement between the researcher and the respondents can be considered in the process of getting informed consent (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011).

Risk of Harm, Maintaining Confidentiality, and Anonymity is the second core principles of ethical considerations. It pertains to the protection of a study's participant so that not even the researcher can link the participants with the data provided, as well as the avoidance of disclosing the participant's identity to anybody other than authorized individuals (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011).

Notably, the participant's safety and the protection of their identity and personal information was assured by the researcher, and viewed them as valued research participants. To produce a spotless data collection, the researcher eliminated identities. A clean data collection has no information may be used to identify the respondents such as names or address (such as identifying information might be stored elsewhere, in separated, protected files).

Conflicts of Interest is the third core aspect of ethical considerations. It recognizes the existing relationships or previous activities by the researcher could result in conflict of interest, which must be transparently revealed in an ethics approval application so the committee can provide advise on how to address the conflict. Additionally, it occurs when a person prioritizes their personal interests or commitments over their responsibilities as a researcher, or is perceived to prioritize them over their duties and responsibilities. Conflicts of interest may be actual, hypothetical, or perceived and may involve incentives in money or in nonmonetary rewards. Conflicts of interest may impair a researcher's objectivity and judgment, or may perceived to affect, which undermines the reliability of the findings (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011).

In this view, there was no external factor in relation to the researcher affecting the outcomes of the research activity because the respondents were also students, the researcher has no conflict of interest in the study. Conflict of interest only arises when the researcher has the power to coerce respondents into participating through blackmailing, termination of benefits, or other forms of punishment, such as: teachers who would force or threaten to fail their students if they do not answer the survey, or principals who threaten to terminate teachers if they do not answer the survey.

Results and Discussion

Presented in this section are the discussions of the data on the mediation analysis of self-regulation on the relationship between mathematical disposition and mathematics among first-year mathematics education students. This chapter presents the data results on the level of mathematical disposition in terms of cognitive, affective, and conative; the level of mathematics proficiency; and the level of self-regulation in terms of intrinsic, identified, introjected, and external.

This also includes the significant relationship between mathematical disposition and mathematics proficiency, significant relationship between mathematical disposition and self-regulation, significant relationship between self-regulation and mathematics proficiency, and the mediation analysis between mathematical disposition and mathematics proficiency via self-regulation. The presentations were done in parallel with the research objectives.

Level of Mathematical Disposition in Terms of Cognitive

The level of mathematical disposition was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, cognitive. The responses of the involved students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 2 is the level of mathematical disposition in terms of cognitive. The data revealed that the level of mathematic disposition in terms of cognitive had a total mean of 3.98 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of mathematical disposition in terms of cognitive is oftentimes manifested.

The highest mean is 4.08 which means high. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the involved respondents. This is from item no. 4—trying to connect math problems I am dealing with to other problems in math.

In contrast, the lowest mean is 3.86 which means high. This implies that the item is oftentimes manifested by the respondents of the study. This is from item no. 2—trying to develop and evaluate mathematical arguments to explain problem solving in math class even though I am not asked.

Table 2. *Level of Mathematical Disposition in Terms of Cognitive*

	<i>Cognitive</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	using mathematical reasoning and proof to explain how I solve problems in maths even though I was not asked.	4.00	High
2.	trying to develop and evaluate mathematical arguments to explain problem solving in math class even though I am not asked.	3.86	High
3.	trying to justify a statement I made in math class.	3.93	High
4.	trying to connect math problems I am dealing with to other problems in math.	4.08	High
5.	always trying to see how problems, concepts, mathematical ideas have to do with other non-math classes.	4.05	High
	Overall	3.98	High

Level of Mathematical Disposition in Terms of Affective

The level of mathematical disposition was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, affective. The responses of first-year mathematics education students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 3 is the level of mathematical disposition in terms of affective. The data revealed that the level of mathematical disposition in terms of affective had a total mean of 3.91 with a descriptive equivalent categorized as high. This high descriptive equivalent of the total mean implies that the level of mathematical disposition in terms of affective is oftentimes manifested by the students under the mathematics education in the first-year level.

The highest mean among the items in the affective domain of mathematical disposition is 4.20 which means high. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the first-year mathematics education students. This is from item no. 2—love working on math problems during my studies.

In opposition, the lowest mean among the items in the affective domain of mathematical disposition is 3.68 with a descriptive equivalence of high. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the first-year students of mathematics education. This is from item no. 4—getting excited when I have to take math exams.

Table 3. *Level of Mathematical Disposition in Terms of Affective*

	<i>Affective</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	love doing math with an environment outside of lectures.	4.08	High
2.	love working on math problems during my studies.	4.20	High
3.	having no trouble understanding concepts in mathematics.	3.72	High
4.	getting excited when I have to take math exams.	3.68	High
5.	getting excited when I have to do math in math class.	3.89	High
	Overall	3.91	High

Level of Mathematical Disposition in Terms of Conative

The level of mathematical disposition was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, conative. The responses of first-year mathematics education students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 4 is the level of mathematical disposition in terms of conative. The data revealed that the level of mathematical disposition in terms of conative had total mean of 4.20 with a descriptive equivalent categorized as high. This high descriptive equivalent indicated that the level of mathematical disposition in terms of conative is oftentimes manifested by the first-year students of mathematics education.

The highest mean among the items in the conative domain of mathematical disposition is 4.38 with a descriptive equivalent categorized as very high. This means that the item is always observed by the involved respondents. This is from item no. 1—believing that with persistent effort in learning math, I can overcome any challenges in understanding it.

On the other hand, the lowest mean among the items is 4.08 with a descriptive equivalent categorized as high. This high descriptive equivalent means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the first-year mathematics education students. This is from item no. 2—figuring something out in math if I persist, even if I do not grasp it quickly in the beginning.

Table 4. *Level of Mathematical Disposition in Terms of Conative*

	<i>Conative</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	believing that with persistent effort in learning math, I can overcome any challenges in understanding it.	4.38	Very High
2.	figuring something out in math if I persist, even if I do not grasp it quickly in the beginning.	4.08	High
3.	trying if there were some things in high school math that I just could not get.	4.20	High
4.	doing well if I persist if I am having difficulties in math.	4.14	High
5.	figuring out the mathematics if I do not give up right away.	4.22	High
	Overall	4.20	High

Summary on the Level of Mathematical Disposition

Presented in Table 5 is the overall level of mathematical disposition in terms of cognitive, affective, and conative. The data revealed that the level of mathematical disposition of first-year students of mathematics education had a total mean of 4.03 with the descriptive equivalent categorized as high. This high descriptive equivalent indicates that the level of mathematical disposition as perceived by the students is oftentimes manifested.

Further, the highest mean among the three domains of mathematical disposition is 4.20 with the descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of mathematical disposition in terms of conative is most oftentimes manifested among the three domains.

In contrast, the lowest indicator is affective which obtained a mean of 3.91 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of mathematical disposition in terms of affective is the least oftentimes manifested among the three domains.

Additionally, cognitive domain obtained a mean of 3.98 which means high. This indicates that the level of mathematical disposition in terms of cognitive is oftentimes manifested.

Table 5. *Summary on the Level of Mathematical Disposition*

<i>Mathematical Disposition</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
Cognitive	3.98	High
Affective	3.91	High
Conative	4.20	High
Overall	4.03	High

Level of Mathematics Proficiency

The level of mathematics proficiency of first-year mathematics education students was measured through a test questionnaire with 25 items covering the topics in the course, College and Advanced Algebra. The response of the 92 respondents was presented and analyzed below.

Table 6. *Level of Mathematics Proficiency*

<i>Data</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
6	2	2.2%		
7	1	1.1%		
8	4	4.3%		
9	1	1.1%		
10	3	3.3%		
11	4	4.3%		
12	2	2.2%		
13	4	4.3%		
14	3	3.3%		
15	5	5.4%		
16	7	7.6%	17.37	Very Good
17	6	6.5%		
18	5	5.4%		
19	5	5.4%		
20	6	6.5%		
21	13	14.1%		
22	9	9.8%		
23	8	8.7%		
24	3	3.3%		
25	1	1.1%		
Total	92	100%		

Legend: 1 – 5 Poor, 6 – 10 Fair, 11 – 15 Good, 16 – 20 Very Good, 21 – 25 Excellent

The level of mathematics proficiency of the first-year mathematics education students is presented, analyzed, and interpreted. The summary of the data is shown in Table 6. The list of scores ranges from 6 to 25 with an overall average score of 17.37 out of 25, or qualitatively interpreted as very good. Further, more than half of the test takers were able to get a score of above the median score, which is 15.5. The score with the highest frequency is 21 which was obtained by 13 students. On the contrary, the scores with the least frequency are 7, 9, and a perfect score, 25, which were obtained by only 1 student each.

There were no students whose scores fall under the poor level (1-5) of mathematics proficiency; 11 students (11.96%) whose scores fall under the fair level (6-10); 18 students (19.57%) under the good level (11-15), which can be labeled as the average level; 29 students (31.52%) under the very good level (16-20); and 34 students (36.96%) under the excellent level (21-25).

Hence, the summary of results stipulates that the mathematical proficiency of first-year students under the mathematics education program was satisfactory. This indicates that first-year education students possess a foundational understanding of algebraic concepts, yet still need further guidance and support to advance their skills in this area.

Level of Self-regulation in Terms of Intrinsic

The level of self-regulation was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, intrinsic. The responses of the involved respondents on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 7 is the level of self-regulation of students in terms of intrinsic. The data revealed that the level of self-regulation in terms of intrinsic has a total mean of 4.21 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This implies that the level of self-regulation of the students in terms of intrinsic is oftentimes manifested.

The highest mean is 4.34 which means very high. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the respondents. This is from item no. 2—working on my classwork because I want to learn new things. In contrast, the lowest mean is 4.09 but with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the respondents of the study. This is from item no. 4—working on my classwork because I enjoy solving tasks.

Table 7. *Level of Self-regulation in Terms of Intrinsic*

	<i>Intrinsic</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	working on classwork because it is fun.	4.24	High
2.	working on my classwork because I want to learn new things.	4.34	Very High
3.	working on my classwork because I enjoy thinking and reflecting about things.	4.21	High
4.	working on my classwork because I enjoy solving tasks.	4.09	High
5.	working on my classwork because I love mathematics.	4.17	High
	Overall	4.21	High

Level of Self-regulation in Terms of Identified

The level of self-regulation was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, identified. The responses of first-year students under the mathematics education program on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 8 is the level of self-regulation of first-year mathematics education students in terms of identified. The data revealed that the level of self-regulation in terms of identified had a total mean of 4.42 with a descriptive equivalent categorized as very high. This very high descriptive equivalent indicates that the level of self-regulation of first-year mathematics education students in terms of identified is always manifested.

The highest mean among the items in the identified domain of self-regulation is 4.51 which is descriptively categorized as very high. This means that the item is always manifested by the first-year students under the mathematics education program. This is from item no. 1—working on my classwork so in the future, I can continue my education. On the other hand, the lowest mean is 4.36 with a descriptive equivalent categorized as very high. This means that the item is always manifested by the first-year mathematics education students. This is from item no. 2—working on my classwork because it will give me better career choices.

Table 8. *Level of Self-regulation in Terms of Identified*

	<i>Identified</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	working on my classwork so in the future, I can continue my education.	4.51	Very High
2.	working on my classwork because it will give me better career choices.	4.36	Very High
3.	working on my classwork because the knowledge in the subject will allow me to get a better job.	4.37	Very High
4.	working on my classwork because the things that I learn here will be useful in the future.	4.37	Very High
5.	working on my classwork because I believe that the things I learn here can be applied in real life.	4.48	Very High
	Overall	4.42	Very High

Level of Self-regulation in Terms of Introjected

The level of self-regulation was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, introjected. The responses of first-year mathematics education students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 9 is the level of self-regulation of first-year mathematics education students in terms of introjected. The data revealed that the level of self-regulation in terms of introjected had a total mean of 3.78 with a descriptive equivalent categorized as high. This indicates that the level of self-regulation of first-year mathematics education students in terms of introjected strategy is oftentimes manifested.

The highest mean among the items in the introjected domain of self-regulation is 4.15 which is descriptively categorized as high. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the respondents. This is from item no. 4—working on my classwork because I would feel ashamed of myself if I do not try.

In contrast, the lowest mean among the items on the same domain is 3.49 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This high descriptive equivalent indicates that the item is oftentimes manifested by the first-year mathematics education students. This is from item no. 3—working on my classwork because I want other students to think I am quite good.

Table 9. Level of Self-regulation in Terms of Introjected

<i>Introjected</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	working on my classwork because I want the teacher to think I am a good student.	3.74	High
2.	working on my classwork because otherwise I would have a guilty conscience.	3.96	High
3.	working on my classwork because I want other students to think I am quite good.	3.49	High
4.	working on my classwork because I would feel ashamed of myself if I do not try.	4.15	High
5.	working on my classwork so that my classmates will compliment my productivity.	3.57	High
Overall		3.78	High

Level of Self-regulation in Terms of External

The level of self-regulation was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, external. The responses of first-year mathematics education students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 10 is the level of self-regulation of first-year mathematics education students in terms of external. The data revealed that the level of self-regulation in terms of external had a total mean of 4.01 with a descriptive equivalent categorized as high. This indicates that the level of self-regulation of first-year students under the mathematics education program in terms of external is oftentimes manifested.

The highest mean among the items in the external domain of self-regulation is 4.35 which is descriptively classified as very high. This means that the item is always manifested by the students. This is from item no. 3—working on my classwork because otherwise I would get bad grades.

On the other hand, the lowest mean among the items on the same domain of self-regulation is 3.71 which is descriptively categorized as high. This high descriptive equivalent means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the respondents of the study. This is from item no. 5—working on my classwork so that I could get rewards from my parents.

Table 10. Level of Self-regulation in Terms of External

<i>External</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	working on my classwork because otherwise I would get into trouble at home.	3.74	High
2.	working on my classwork because otherwise I would get into trouble with my teacher.	4.00	High
3.	working on my classwork because otherwise I would get bad grades.	4.35	Very High
4.	working on my classwork because that is what I am supposed to do.	4.24	High
5.	working on my classwork so that I could get rewards from my parents.	3.71	High
Overall		4.01	High

Summary on the Level of Self-regulation

Presented in Table 11 is the overall level of self-regulation in terms of intrinsic, identified, introjected, and external. The data revealed that the level of self-regulation of first-year mathematics education students had a total mean of 4.10 with the descriptive equivalent classified as high. This indicates that the level of self-regulation of the first-year students under the mathematics education program is oftentimes manifested.

Further, the highest mean among the four domains is 4.42 with the descriptive equivalent of very high. This indicates that the level of self-regulation in terms of identified is always manifested.

In contrast, the lowest indicator is introjected which obtained a mean of 3.78 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of self-regulation in terms of introjected is oftentimes manifested.

Furthermore, the intrinsic domain of self-regulation obtained a mean of 4.21 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of self-regulation in terms of intrinsic is oftentimes manifested.

Lastly, external domain of self-regulation obtained a mean of 4.01 which means high. This indicates that the level of self-regulation in

terms of external is oftentimes manifested.

Table 11. *Summary on the Level of Self-regulation*

<i>Self-regulation</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
Intrinsic	4.21	High
Identified	4.42	Very High
Introjected	3.78	High
External	4.01	High
Overall	4.10	High

Significant Relationship between Mathematical Disposition and Mathematics Proficiency

Presented in Table 12 is the result of the significant relationship between mathematical disposition and mathematics proficiency. The result revealed that the strength of the relationship between mathematical disposition and mathematics proficiency of the involved respondents is $r(90) = .555$, $p < .001$. Since the probability value ($p < .001$) is less than the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$), the null hypothesis is rejected. This indicates that there is a significant positive relationship between mathematical disposition and mathematics proficiency among first-year mathematics education students.

Table 12. *Significant relationship between Mathematical Disposition and Mathematics Proficiency*

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Decision @ = 0.05</i>
Mathematical Disposition	4.03	.555	<.001	Ho Rejected
Mathematics Proficiency	17.37			

Significant Relationship between Mathematical Disposition and Self-regulation

Presented in Table 13 is the result of the significant relationship between mathematical disposition and self-regulation. The result showed that the strength of the relationship between mathematical disposition and self-regulation of the involved respondents is $r(90) = .716$, $p < .001$. Since the probability value ($p < .001$) is less than the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$), null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is a significant positive relationship between mathematical disposition and self-regulation among first-year mathematics education students.

Table 13. *Significant relationship between Mathematical Disposition and Self-regulation*

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Decision @ = 0.05</i>
Mathematical Disposition	4.03	.716	<.001	Ho Rejected
Self-regulation	4.10			

Significant Relationship between Self-regulation and Mathematics Proficiency

Presented in Table 14 is the result of the significant relationship between self-regulation and mathematics proficiency, $r(90) = .426$, $p < .001$. Since the probability value ($p < .001$) is less than the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$), null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is a significant positive relationship between self-regulation and mathematics proficiency.

Table 14. *Significant relationship between Self-regulation and Mathematics Proficiency*

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Decision @ = 0.05</i>
Self-regulation	4.10	.426	<.001	Ho Rejected
Mathematics Proficiency	17.37			

The Mediation Analysis of Self-regulation on the Mathematical Disposition and Mathematics Proficiency among First-Year Mathematics Education Students

Preacher and Hayes mediation analysis approach was utilized in this study to determine if self-regulation mediates the relationship between mathematical disposition and mathematics proficiency among first-year mathematics education students. It is a regression-based bootstrap approach similar to SEM (Structural Equation Modeling) that is used for analyzing mediation. It consists of two steps that reflect the recommendation for mediation analysis. In step 1, the direct and indirect effect are tested for significance. Step 2 involves defining the type of effect and mediation, which is classified into partial and full mediation.

Full mediation is achieved if the direct effect is not significant and the indirect effect is significant. It means that only the indirect effect via the mediator exists. On the other hand, partial mediation happens when the direct effect is significant.

Mediation Analysis

It can be observed in Table 15 the direct effect of mathematical disposition (IV) on mathematics proficiency (DV). The result yielded an estimate of 4.342 and standard error (SE) 1.052 with $p < .001$ or significant, ($\beta = 4.342$, $SE = 1.052$, 95% CI [2.280, 6.403]).

Additionally, it is observed that every unit increased in the mathematical disposition (IV) will entice 4.342 increase in the mathematics proficiency (DV). The results stipulate that the mathematical disposition (IV) is significantly influencing mathematics proficiency (DV).

This indicates that the mathematical disposition (IV) has a direct effect on mathematics proficiency (DV). Hence, as the mathematical disposition (IV) increases, mathematics proficiency (DV) increases dramatically as well.

Table 15. *Direct Effect*

	Estimate	Std. Error	z-value	p	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower	Upper
IV → DV	4.342	1.052	4.128	< .001	2.280	6.403

It can be noticed in Table 16 the indirect effect of mathematical disposition (IV) on self-regulation (MV) and on mathematics proficiency (DV). The result yielded a beta (β) of 0.358 and standard error (SE) 0.754 with $p = .635$ or insignificant, ($\beta = 0.358$, $SE = 0.754$, 95% CI [-1.120, 1.835]).

Furthermore, it can be perceived that every unit increased in the mathematical disposition (IV) will entice 0.358 increase to the mathematics proficiency (DV) as it goes through the self-regulation (MV).

Based on the result, it shows that the mathematical disposition (IV) has no indirect effect on the mathematics proficiency (DV) through self-regulation (MV). That means the mathematical disposition (IV) can directly influence the mathematics proficiency (DV) without the presence of the mediating variable, self-regulation.

Table 16. *Indirect Effect*

	Estimate	Std. Error	z-value	p	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower	Upper
IV → MV → DV	0.358	0.754	0.474	0.635	-1.120	1.835

It can be observed in Table 17 the total effects of mathematical disposition (IV) on mathematics proficiency (DV). The result yielded a beta of 4.699 which is from the sum of each beta in Table 14 and Table 15, and standard error (SE) 0.735 with $p < .001$ or significant, ($\beta = 4.699$, $SE = 0.735$, 95% CI [3.258, 6.140]).

Table 17. *Total Effects*

	Estimate	Std. Error	z-value	p	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower	Upper
IV → DV	4.699	0.735	6.392	< .001	3.258	6.140

Also, as shown in the results, it could be inferred that in every unit increased in the mathematical disposition (IV) will entice 4.699 increase to the mathematics proficiency (DV). The result stipulates that the mathematical disposition (IV) is significantly affecting the mathematics proficiency (DV).

Additionally, the Table 18 below provides further information as to why the mediating effect of self-regulation is insignificant to the relationship of mathematical disposition and mathematics proficiency. It can be observed in the table that the effect of self-regulation (MV) to mathematics proficiency (DV) is not significant, $\beta = .55$, $p = .635$. Further, their confidence interval shows negative lower interval, and for an interval that ranges from negative to positive values, we know the interval contains zero (or the null value), then it suggests that there is really no significant effect, because the null hypothesis is accepted when the confidence interval includes zero. On the other hand, the table shows that there is a significant effect of mathematical disposition (IV) to mathematics proficiency (DV), $\beta = 4.34$, $p < .001$. Similarly, there is a significant effect of mathematical disposition (DV) to self-regulation (MV), $\beta = .65$, $p < .001$.

Table 18. *Path Coefficients*

	Estimate	Std. Error	z-value	p	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower	Upper
MV → DV	0.549	1.156	0.475	0.635	-1.716	2.814
IV → DV	4.342	1.052	4.128	< .001	2.280	6.403
IV → MV	0.652	0.066	9.835	< .001	0.522	0.781

The model in Figure 1 shows the significant relationship between mathematical disposition (IV) and mathematics proficiency (DV) through the mediating effect of self-regulation (MV). In Path A, mathematical disposition (IV) has a significant influence with self-regulation (MV), $\beta = .65$, $p < .001$. In Path B, self-regulation (MV) was also reported significantly influencing mathematics proficiency (DV), $\beta = .55$, $p < .001$. In Path C, mathematical disposition (IV) was positively predictive of mathematics proficiency (DV), $\beta = 4.3$, $p < .001$.

Apparently, it explained that because of direct effect is significant while the indirect effect is insignificant, then the self-regulation (MV) does not mediate the relationship mathematical disposition (IV) and mathematics proficiency (DV) of first-year mathematics education students. Hence, these results stipulate the relationship between mathematical disposition and mathematics proficiency was neither partially nor fully mediated by the indirect pathway through self-regulation, a claim that was also supported in Table 16 by the estimation of a significant indirect effect.

Figure 3. Path Plot Showing the Variables of the Study

Conclusions

This section consists of the overall summary of the study, particularly the results, and each of their implications. Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were drawn in answer to the objectives:

The level of mathematical disposition of the first-year mathematics education students who demonstrated disposition in math is high. Thus, fostering positive attitude towards mathematics, as perceived by students, empowers them to gain interest in learning mathematics and to develop critical thinking and mathematical skills such as problem-solving.

On the other hand, the level of self-regulation among first-year mathematics education students who demonstrated self-regulation is high. Thus, cultivating self-regulation in learning mathematics and working on tasks enable students gain success in mathematics. Also, a high level of self-regulation of the students implies that they put value on the importance and relevance of mathematics in life.

Moreover, the level of mathematics proficiency among first-year mathematics education students who is satisfactory. Thus, the students are already beyond average level in mathematics during at their first year in college. However, continuous efforts to improve mathematics education and support learners in reaching beyond satisfactory proficiency levels are essential for individual success and societal progress.

Based on the findings, there is a significant relationship between mathematical disposition and mathematics proficiency, as it is affirmed that mathematics proficiency in a general context is more likely to be affected by mathematical disposition. Therefore, as perceived by students, mathematical disposition immensely influences their proficiency in mathematics, which stipulates a significant relationship between the two variables.

Based on the study's findings, there is also a significant relationship between mathematical disposition and self-regulation. Therefore, students' mathematical disposition and self-regulation, as perceived by students, are mutually reinforcing throughout their mathematics learning process. Therefore, as perceived by students, self-regulation is immensely influenced by their mathematical disposition, which stipulates a significant relationship between the two variables.

Also, there is a significant relationship between self-regulation and mathematics proficiency. Therefore, students' self-regulation immensely influences their mathematics proficiency, which stipulates a significant relationship between the two variables.

Furthermore, the mediation analysis revealed that self-regulation has no significant mediating role on the relationship between mathematical disposition and mathematics proficiency. While self-regulation is an important factor in academic achievement, its role may not be influential in the specific context of mathematics proficiency. This finding underscores the complexity of factors influencing mathematical ability and suggests avenues for further research to better understand the mechanisms at play. Understanding these relationships can inform interventions and educational strategies aimed at improving mathematics proficiency.

Lastly, the result did not agree to the Goal-Setting Theory of Locke (1968) in terms of the mediating role of self-regulation. Additionally, the theory did not explicitly mention that self-regulation mediates the relationship between mathematical disposition.

Therefore, the result contradicts to the presumption that the linkage between mathematical disposition and mathematics proficiency is mediated by self-regulation as supported by the said theory.

The suggestions of the researcher are established based on the results and the wholeness of the paper. In light of the aforementioned findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

It is recommended to continue fostering a positive attitude towards mathematics among first-year mathematics education students who demonstrate high mathematical disposition. Providing opportunities for students to engage with real-world applications of mathematics and incorporating interactive teaching methods can further enhance their interest and motivation in learning mathematics, ultimately leading to the development of critical thinking and problem-solving skills.

Given that affective domain of mathematical dispositions had obtained the lowest mean among the three indicators, it is highly suggested that students must foster the tendency to like and love mathematics through continual engaging in math-related tasks in school and even in their daily life, and erase the mindset that mathematics is difficult to learn because it is easier than they might think. Also, it is recommended that teachers must employ strategies on their teaching that effectively hit the affective domain of learning.

To build upon the already high level of self-regulation observed among first-year mathematics education students, it is advisable to implement strategies that further cultivate self-regulation skills in learning mathematics. This may include setting clear goals, providing feedback, and teaching self-monitoring techniques. Emphasizing the importance and relevance of mathematics in various contexts can also reinforce students' intrinsic motivation to regulate their learning effectively.

Further, since introjected self-regulation had obtained the lowest mean and which is way far from intrinsic, identified, and external self-regulation, it is important to look further on the importance and its impact on the students. It is recommended to foster a bit of introjected self-regulation because this kind of extrinsic motivation helps students attain their responsibilities, achieve and excel more in mathematics through having a sense of duty or obligation that comes from external pressure like expectation from other people.

While the current level of mathematics proficiency among first-year mathematics education students is satisfactory, ongoing efforts to improve mathematics education should be prioritized. Providing additional support and resources tailored to individual student needs can help them surpass satisfactory proficiency levels. Incorporating collaborative learning environments and utilizing technology-enhanced instructional approaches can further enhance students' mathematical abilities and promote continued growth.

Given the significant relationship between mathematical disposition and mathematics proficiency, it is crucial for educators and policymakers to recognize the impact of students' attitudes towards mathematics on their overall proficiency levels. Efforts should be made to nurture positive mathematical dispositions from an early age and provide support to students who may struggle with negative perceptions of mathematics.

Considering the significant relationship between mathematical disposition and self-regulation, educators should explore strategies that leverage students' positive attitudes towards mathematics to promote the development of self-regulation skills. Encouraging self-reflection, goal-setting, and self-monitoring within the context of mathematics learning can enhance students' ability to regulate their learning effectively and contribute to their overall academic success.

Given the significant relationship between self-regulation and mathematics proficiency, it is essential to prioritize the development of self-regulation skills alongside mathematical content knowledge. Providing explicit instruction on self-regulatory strategies and fostering a supportive learning environment where students feel empowered to take ownership of their learning can lead to improvements in mathematics proficiency over time.

Although the mediation analysis did not find a significant mediating role of self-regulation on the relationship between mathematical disposition and mathematics proficiency, further research is warranted to better understand the intricate interplay between these variables. Exploring additional factors that may influence mathematics proficiency and examining potential moderating variables could provide valuable insights for enhancing mathematics education practices and improving student outcomes. Lastly, the researcher would suggest to conduct the study in a larger number of respondents as it might be one of the factors affecting the result of the mediation analysis.

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